

THE MAIN CRITERIA OF CULTURAL CENTERS IN THE FORMATION OF
CREATIVE ABILITY

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In the formation of creative feelings, it is necessary to pay attention to two important individuals. Teacher and student. The formation of creativity in both individuals will have a different appearance. In the first case, in the formation of this feeling in the student, attention is paid to his opportunities, interests, and free time, while the formation of the creative feeling in the pedagogue employee has been proven in practice.

When we hear the word "creative", we immediately think of areas of human activity such as marketing and advertising. This is because the work of specialists in these fields is directly related to the creation of new ideas.

At the same time, creativity has become an important quality that a candidate must have in the fight for a high-paying position. Someone says that it is like a genius and cannot be developed. someone, on the contrary, offers to develop this quality and guarantees success for any person. Nowadays, you can come across hundreds of trainings aimed at developing creative thinking everywhere.

If we imagine creativity at the everyday level, it can be called invention, that is, the ability to achieve set goals and find a way out of an existing difficult situation, to use objects and equipment in a non-standard way. On the surface, it may seem like a wonderful, but also simple thing. The thought arises: "Why didn't I think of this before?" A non-trivial approach to problem solving is creativity.

Translated from English, this word looks like "creating" or "inventing", but it refers not only to material things. As you can see, this is a very useful process. But where does it come from? According to American psychologist Maslow, this ability of a person is inherent in nature, but it can be lost in the process of education and external influence. Various tests, personal questionnaires and simulations of various situations are used to assess the level of a person's creative abilities.

Let's take a closer look at the process of creating ideas yourself. Maybe smart ideas don't come out of nowhere and just pop into your head. English psychologist Graham Wallace distinguished 4 stages of creative problem solving.

The first is preparation. At this stage, a task or problem is formed and the first attempts are made to solve it. Next comes the incubation stage. Here, a person, as a rule, is distracted by other objects or actions and confuses the ways of intuitively getting to the heart of the problem. At the final stage - this is verification, that is, they implement the solution. In fact, in order for the creativity of thinking to manifest, it is necessary to turn off the mind and fully trust the subconscious. That's why the second step is so important. Most of the time, we interfere with ourselves, we try to consciously find a solution in situations known to us, but this does not help us

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to find something new. Our complexes or psychological blocks, the fear of looking stupid can also become a problem of creativity. All this makes creative thinking difficult.

Criteria of creative thinking.

Many tests are aimed at evaluating the criteria of creativity in a person. At the moment, the most famous test was created by psychologist Paul Torrance. This will allow you to determine this starting level. Here are a few criteria:

fluency;

originality;

flexibility (allows to identify false identity);

metaphor, that is, the ability to see the complex as simple and vice versa;

sensitivity;

development;

satisfaction.

Creative methods.

Creativity techniques are methods and techniques designed to facilitate the process of creating new ideas and solutions. They are designed to help clarify problems, speed up the process of finding solutions, increase the number of ideas, and expand the industry of the problem. But it should be noted that this is not an algorithm, as a result of which you will definitely find a solution. Methods only increase the probability of good and correct ideas, they organize the search process itself and make it more effective.

What is creativity? It is primarily a tool to get something new and original. Stimulation techniques are used in all areas of life, for example, engineers and inventors successfully use methods such as morphological analysis and TRIZ (theory of invention problem solving). Lateral thinking techniques are widely used in advertising and marketing, and the SCAMPER technique is used to create completely new products. Also available globally. These include Brainstorming and The Walt Disney Method. They have found applications in almost all areas. Sometimes graphic images are also used, for example, the method of mind mapping, which is aimed at further development of creativity.

The golden rule for not breaking out of the shell of creativity and developing it regularly is this - First of all, you need to get rid of stereotypes in your thinking and acquire the ability to think outside the box. This can be helped by exercises that should become a habit for you.

For example, travel home or work. It usually follows the same path. Try walking back to the bus stop or part of the bus journey. Try to change the path and find new options every day.

Everything new and untried is useful: places, menus, actions, clothes and even thoughts. Creativity, whose meaning is directly related to creativity, can help develop art or craft lessons. Exercises such as reading backwards (from bottom to top or from right to left) are also very useful and uplifting at the same time.

Try suggesting 10 exotic names like Diosthenes, Hematina or Eyergestio. Draw a non-existent animal, name it, think about where it lives and what it eats. Take any word and imagine it is an abbreviation, open it. All these exercises are simple and fun, but they will help you develop creativity.

Creativity is divided into five important types:

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1. Scientific creativity - involves the search for things that already exist, but do not correspond to our consciousness. It is characteristic of the study of phenomena in the world and various forms of development.

2. Technical creativity is close to scientific creativity, and in fact implies the creation of practical changes, discoveries and discoveries. In its process, new material values were created for the society.

3. Artistic creativity is the creation of aesthetic values, images that evoke spiritual experiences in a person. When you discover something objective and for yourself - in the process of creation it is important to separate the subjectivity from which you create something for society.

4. Co-creation is a level of perception that allows the viewer or listener to understand the deep meaning of the work behind the event, that is, the subtext that the author wants to convey to the viewer.

5. Pedagogical creativity is a new discovery in the field of pedagogical activity. It can be innovation - an unconventional way of solving problems, and innovation - the use of old methods of teaching in a new environment. Finding an unexpected pedagogical decision and applying it to specific situations is called improvisation and is common.

Let's consider the factors that form a creative node in a child or student.

As it is known in childhood, a child's dreams and fantasies play a very important role. But how many people think that children's creative abilities should be developed. Unfortunately, most adults do not pay enough attention to the development of a child's imagination, which significantly limits the opportunities of children in the future. Creativity plays a very important role in everyone's life. Imagination and fantasy help people in both relationships and work, but most importantly, creative people can express their own identity that helps them succeed in any business. Thus, even if the child does not suffer from a lack of imagination, parents should pay attention to the development of their creative abilities.

Identification and formation of creative abilities.

The main development of creative abilities in everyday life is carried out through play. In the game, children will probably like games that are able to determine the most interesting range of activities for children. Therefore, the game is one of the main ways to identify creative abilities. Psychologists have developed special tests in the form of a game that allow you to determine the level of development of your imagination and the way of thinking of a child. Some children act on the power of imagination, while others tend to capture images from memory. Sometimes children refuse to participate in such games, which indicates the need for a special approach to the child. Creating the necessary conditions for the development of children's creative abilities also plays a big role. Parents should not only give the child the opportunity to develop, but also actively participate. In no case can you put pressure on the child, allow him to play the game or participate in practical arts. In particular, this error is allowed with the development of musical abilities. Since the child's interest in music is not enough, parents are in a hurry to send him to a music school. In order to develop any creative ability in children, it is necessary not only to determine the inclination of the baby, but also to carry out serious work that will strengthen the desire to develop in the right direction.

The development of artistic abilities can begin up to 1 year. At this age, children learn about objects and their properties. It is recommended to come across a variety of things for paper, bright pencils and markers in the child's view. By the age of 2-3, the introductory period begins, children

make arbitrary lines and shapes and are very interested in colors. First, parents should monitor the child's safety. When children turn 3, parents participate. First, it is recommended to draw lines, for example, a circle is like an apple, a line to a path. It comes down to drawings with children's drawings, there is a transition from arbitrary drawings on paper to the desire to produce a meaningful picture. During this period, it is important to encourage and support the baby, to give him freedom in his work. It is recommended when a child develops enough interest in drawing to be sent to an art school.

The level of development of personal abilities is divided into two types:

- reproductive, when a person demonstrates the ability to successfully acquire various skills, acquire and apply knowledge, as well as perform activities based on a previously suggested model or idea;
- creative, if a person has the ability to create something new, original.

In the process of successfully acquiring knowledge and skills, a person moves from one level of development to another.

In addition, according to Teplov's theory, abilities are divided into general and special. General ones are those that appear in any field of activity, special ones appear in a certain field.

The following levels of development of this quality are distinguished:

- ability;
- talent;
- talent;
- genius.

To form a person's talent, there should be an organic combination of general and special abilities, and their rapid development is also necessary. A person is called a genius if his activity left a clear mark on the development of society. Genius is the highest level of development of abilities possessed by several. This quality is inextricably linked with a great personality. Unlike other levels of development of abilities, genius is characterized by the fact that it usually exhibits its own "profile". Any side of the monstrous personality will inevitably dominate, which will lead to the manifestation of certain abilities. Identifying abilities is still one of the most difficult tasks of psychology. At different times, many scientists have proposed their research methods for this quality. However, at present, there is no methodology that allows to determine the ability of a person with absolute accuracy, as well as to determine its level.

The main problem is that abilities were measured quantitatively, the level of development of general abilities was deduced. But in fact, they are a quality indicator that should be looked at with dynamic indicators. Different psychologists have put forward their own methods to measure this quality. For example, L. S. Vygotsky proposed to assess the child's ability through the zone of proximal development. This involves a dual diagnosis, when the child first solves the problem together with an adult, and then independently.

The level of intellectual development of a person refers to his ability to use his mind for thinking, understanding, listening, making decisions, observing relationships, perceiving and other mental operations. One of the most used methods for determining the level of development of this quality is IQ-tests, which offer a certain set of tasks and set time for their completion. The scores earned by taking this test range from 0 to 160 and range from weak to genius. IQ tests are designed for people of all ages.

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Another popular technique - SHTUR also reveals abilities. The level of development of intellectual abilities in schoolchildren is to diagnose this method. It includes 6 subtests, each of which includes 15 to 25 tasks of the same type.

The first two subtests are aimed at determining the general consciousness of schoolchildren, and the rest show the following:

- the ability to find similarities;
- logical classifications;
- logical generalization;
- finding the rule for building a series of numbers.

The method is designed for group studies and is limited in time. High statistical indicators of SHTUR methodology allow to assess the reliability of the determined results.

A universal method of measuring the level of creativity is the Guilford technique, which is available in various modifications. Creative qualities that can be determined using this method:

- originality in forming associations;
- semantic and semantic flexibility;
- the ability to create new ideas;
- level of development of figurative thinking.

In this study, the subject offers various situations, which can only be solved by a non-standard approach that assumes the presence of creative abilities.

Qualities that the respondent must have in order to successfully pass the test:

- perception and correct understanding of proposed tasks;
- working memory;
- divergence - the ability to find the original in something simple;
- convergence - the ability to identify an object based on qualitatively different characteristics.

A high level of development of creative abilities, as a rule, implies intellectual development at an appropriate level, as well as the presence of self-confidence, a sense of humor, fluent speech and impulsivity.

The main difference between tests to determine creative abilities and similar tools designed to determine intellectual abilities is the absence of a time limit for solving tasks, a complex structure that offers the possibility of finding several solutions, as well as indirect sentence construction. Each task successfully completed in the test indicates the presence of abilities for a specific area of creative activity.

Other methods of diagnosing the level of development of abilities

Human abilities can manifest themselves at any age. However, the sooner they are identified, the greater the likelihood of their successful development. Therefore, at the moment, work is required in educational institutions from childhood, during which the levels of development of abilities in children are determined. According to the results of working with schoolchildren, trainings are held on the development of the determined inclination to a certain area. Such work cannot be limited only to the school, parents should also take an active part in the work in this direction.

The most commonly used methods for diagnosing abilities, both general and specific:

- "Everyone's Problem", designed to assess the appropriateness of thinking, that is, the extent to which a person can focus on the task at hand.

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- "Study of memory using the technique of memorizing ten words" aimed at identifying memory processes.
- "Verbal imagination" - to determine the level of development of creative abilities, first of all, imagination.
- "Remember and make a point" - diagnostics of attention.
- "Compasses" - studying the features of spatial thinking.
- "Anagrams" - the definition of combinatorial abilities.
- "Analytical mathematical ability" - identifying similar tendencies.
- "Abilities" - determining the success of performing activities in a certain area.
- "Your creative age", aimed at determining the compatibility of passport age with psychological age.
- "Your creativity" - diagnosis of creative possibilities.

The number of techniques and their exact list is determined depending on the goals of the diagnostic examination. In this case, the final result of the work is not to determine the ability of the person. The level of development of abilities should be constantly increased, therefore, after diagnosis, work should be carried out to improve some qualities.

Conditions are one of the most important criteria for improving this quality. Talent refers to a set of various abilities that are sufficiently highly developed and enable a person to successfully master any type of activity. In this case, the ability to master is clearly implied, because, among other things, a person must directly master the skills and abilities necessary for the successful implementation of the idea.

Talent is of the following types:

- artistic, implying great achievements in artistic activity;
- general - intellectual or academic, if the levels of development of human abilities are manifested in good results in learning, mastering various knowledge in various scientific fields;
- creative, offering the ability to create new ideas and demonstrate inventiveness;
- social, providing high social intelligence, identifying leadership qualities, as well as having the ability to establish constructive relationships with people and organizational skills;
- practical, manifested in the ability to use one's intelligence to achieve the goals set before a person, to know the strengths and weaknesses of a person and to use this knowledge. In addition, there are types of giftedness in various narrow fields, such as mathematical giftedness, literary giftedness, etc.

Talented people have been of interest for a long time. Some see it as a gift from God, and some see it as a talent that works hard and works on its own. Is it possible to develop certain abilities and what is the gift of a person?

What is talent?

Talent is inherent from birth. They develop by gaining experience and being oriented in the right direction, building skills. Simply put, a person's ability to do better than others. When and how does the ability manifest itself?

A person can be gifted from birth and demonstrate his incomparability from childhood (Mozart is a great example).

A person can express himself with older people like Van Gogh or Gauguin.

There is no less controversy among scholars and critics about what talent is and whether it is unique to any individual. Here the opinions are divided into opposites:

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- Everyone has talent, because everyone is good in a certain area. You can use your amazing skills and develop them through practice.

- Any kind of hard work and daily exercise. A person's abilities manifest themselves over time, with experience.

It is very easy to distinguish gifted people in others, and the observant person must not lose focus.

- Creative people have a lot of energy in their field of interest and they have thoughts all day long.

- Talented people are both introverts and extroverts.

- The peculiarity of gifted people is that they are modest and self-confident at the same time.

- Such people are ready to sacrifice their careers for their loved ones.

- Extraordinary individuals are not always talented in any field, and often in any of them.

Talent and genius should not be confused, because in the second case, a person is considered talented in all areas. In other words, genius is the highest stage of creative manifestations of personality.

There are many talented people in society. History also testifies to this. It is possible to compile a list of outstanding personalities who have made a great contribution to the development of mankind:

William Shakespeare is the genius of world literature, the greatest English playwright and poet.

Leonardo da Vinci - the brightest representative of Renaissance art - the greatest genius of all time.

Isaac Newton is an English physicist who developed the theory of relativity.

A. Navoi is a great thinker and writer.

Z.M. Babur - king and poet, statesman.

Abu Ali ibn Sina is the Sultan of medical science.

Talented individuals lived and worked among our ancestors in the field of art and culture.

Mutal Burkhanov is a great composer.

Mukhtar Ashrafiy is a composer and composer.

Yunus Rajabi is a genius of Uzbek status art.

Botir Zakirov is the founder of Uzbek Estrada art.

Luftkhonim Sarimsokova is a popular actress.

Obid Yunusov - People's Artist.

If we continue the list, there are countless art dargahs, owners of this unique talent and talent.

List of used literature:

1. <https://uz.everaoh.com/>
2. uz.drunkentengu.com – Laura McKinney “Ijodkorlikni rivojlantirish masalalari.”, 5.04.22 y.
3. <https://uz.drunkentengu.com/> – Charles Brown “Inson qobiliyatlari. Qobiliyatni rivojlantirish darajalari: diagnostika usullari, rivojlanish”, 3.02.2021 y.
4. <https://uz.tierient.com/> – “Psixologiyada qobiliyat va daho nima?”

5. Olimov Sh.Sh. Sinfdan tashqari ta'lim-tarbiyaviy ishlar o'quvchilar axloqiy-estetik idealini shakllantirishdagi o'rni. Xalq ta'limi jurnali. 2000 yil 5-son.
6. Pedagogika. A.Q.Munavvarov tahriri ostida.-Toshkent.: O'qituvchi, 1996.
7. Ne'matullayeva, Sh. "MADANIYAT MARKAZLARINING PROFESSIONAL JAMOALAR BILAN HAMKORLIKNI TASHKIL ETISH MASALALARI." *Педагогика и психология в современном мире: теоретические и практические исследования* 2.3 (2023): 25-29.
8. KO, Sh, and S. Sadullayeva. "SSENARIYDA SAN'AT VOSITALARINING O'RNI." *IJODKOR O'QITUVCHI* 3.26 (2023): 102-105.
9. KO'rinov, Sh, and S. Sadullayeva. "MUZEYSHUNOSLIK ISTIQBOLLARI." *IJODKOR O'QITUVCHI* 3.26 (2023): 97-101.
10. Orinov, Sh K., and S. Rozimurodova. "Maqom San'atiga E'tibor Milliy San'atimizga E'tibor." "ONLINE-CONFERENCES" PLATFORM. 2023.
11. O'rinov, Sh K., and G. Halimova. "HAVASKORLIK BADIY JAMOALARI TUSHUNCHASI VA FUNKSIONAL VAZIFASI." *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES*. Vol. 1. No. 2. 2023.
12. KOrinov, Sh, and M. Ismoilova. "BOSHQARUV KONSEPSIYASI VA ASOSIY TUSHUNCHALAR." *PEDAGOGS jurnali* 26.2 (2023): 62-64.
13. KOrinov, Sh, and M. Hasanova. "BOSHQARUV MADANIYATI TARKIBI FUNKSIYALARI MEZONLARI-MADANIYAT MARKAZLARI MISOLIDA." *PEDAGOGS jurnali* 26.2 (2023): 65-66.
14. KOrinov, Sh, and M. Habibullayeva. "ART MENEJER-MARKETING FAOLIYATINING ASOSIY YO'NALISHLARI SIFATIDA." *PEDAGOGS jurnali* 26.2 (2023): 59-61.
15. Xolmo'minov M. Z. O. L. PROFESSOR AZAMAT HAYDAROV KITOBLARIDA MA'NAVIYMA'RIFIY ISLOHOTLAR TAHLILI //Oriental Art and Culture. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 2. – C. 255-263.
16. Kholmuminov M., Qolqanatov A. The Formation of the First Libraries in Uzbekistan and the Role of Increasing the Cultural and Educational Awareness of the Population //International Journal on Integrated Education. – 2021. – T. 4. – №. 12. – C. 146-151.
17. Nilufar M., Kholmuminov M. Requirements for Young Leaders in Culture and Arts Management //Web of Semantic: Universal Journal on Innovative Education. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 3. – C. 5-9.
18. Mo'Minmirzo Zokir O. G. L. et al. TEATR FAOLIYATIDA BOSHQARUV JARAYONLARINI TASHKIL ETISH USULLARI //Oriental Art and Culture. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 2. – C. 57-62.
19. Xolmo'Minov M. M., Qolqanatov A. O'ZBEKISTONDA MADANIY-MA'RIFIY ISHLAR VA KUTUBXONALAR FAOLIYATI (XX ASR TAJRIBALARIDAN) //Oriental Art and Culture. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 1. – C. 281-290.